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ACTIVE IMPRESSIONS OF DESIGN PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Users are assumed to not only receive impressions from products but also generate impressions within their minds. Furthermore, users are thought to have certain anticipations regarding products. We term the feelings concerned with these anticipations as “active impressions.” The purpose of this study is to investigate how active impressions occur in users’ minds by focusing on how media cause these active impressions. The results show that active impressions are involved in users’ feelings toward the products and may be affected by media wherein the impressions are received and generated.

Keywords: Active impression, Cognitive process, Emotional design

INTRODUCTION

Today, design based on emotion has become the focal point of various fields. In particular, the importance of the users’ deep impressions regarding products has been highlighted (Taura et al., 2010). Users are assumed to not only receive impressions from external sources but also generate impressions within their minds. They are also presumed to create mental images of products on the basis of their wants, and to generate new content in the manner of a creator (Vickery and Wunch-Vincent, 2007). In other words, users are thought to have certain anticipations regarding products. First, they receive certain impressions while interacting with products. Next, they might remember past experiences on the basis of the received (given) impressions. Lastly, certain anticipations may result from their remembered memory of the products. We term the feelings concerned with these anticipations as

“active impressions.” These are expected to be essential to the design of “good” products.

ACTIVE IMPRESSIONS

When people look, listen, or use something, they receive impressions. We call these as “passive impressions” (hereafter in this paper, the term “impression” indicates “passive impressions.”). We assume that these passive impressions lead to certain anticipations or imaginations, which are created internally, and we call these as “active impressions.” Some of these processes are thought to be remembrances of past experiences or associations. In cognitive science, cognitive processes are thought to occur as the result of inputted stimulus information followed by the creation of conscious content (Neisser, 1976). This may occur in active impressions. By taking this into account, we construct a model of the active impression forming process, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Model of the active impression forming process.

This cognitive process also includes interactions with stored and remembered experiences (LeDoux, 1996). These are assumed to be associative processes. Hence, in this research, we focus on association.

Figure 2. Example of an active impression.

Figure 2 shows an example of an active impression. When a person looks at an object, he receives certain impressions such like “pretty” and “toy-like.” These are passive impressions. He/she may then remember past experiences such as, “I played with toys,” and may expand his associations: “I played at the park—there were many trees there.” At this point, anticipations and imaginations may be produced: “Have the trees grown? The park may have been enlarged!” These are active impressions. Products that produce active impressions are expected not only to fulfill their pre-defined function but also to generate novel usage that may be created within users’ minds. To do this, it is important to understand how these active impressions are formed. Generally, the visual and auditory senses are essential to the reception of active impressions, which are formed based on visual and auditory stimuli. Hence, different media are assumed to cause different active impressions.

PURPOSE AND METHOD

This study aims to investigate how active impressions occur by focusing on how different media cause different active impressions. In particular, we investigated the differences between light and music. People receive a great deal of information visually (Marr, 1982) as well as auditorily. There are many differences between visual and auditory information. For example, the impressions given by lighting (a source of visual information) are by nature ambiguous, whereas music (a source of auditory information) has the nature of community in its impressions; for example, a tune in a major key gives a bright impression. Hence, we attempt to investigate how differences of modality affect the phenomenon of active impressions.

First, we developed a lighting system to provide stimuli for active impressions. The system’s lighting worked in accordance with the music. Next, to confirm the differences between lighting and music, we performed an experiment based on the structure of opera: participants read part of a story, either viewed the lighting produced by the system or listened to the music, and then described what they anticipated would happen next. In an opera, an extra-dramatic interpolation that set the mode of the play was used to elicit anticipation (Sadie and Tyrrell, 2001). We assumed that the anticipation is an active impression; thus, the stage effect in opera is thought to be an exemplar of products that make users produce active impressions. Therefore, we used an actual opera story and its intermission music in the experiment. Finally, we analyzed the described anticipations by focusing on active impressions.

PRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENT

The purpose of our chosen experiment was to analyze the differences between the effects of music and lighting; mid-way through reading a story, one group was presented with music and the other group was presented with lighting. We developed the lighting system and conducted the experiment (Yamada et al., 2011).

PRODUCTION

For lighting in the experiment, we produced a lighting system that varied color and luminance by changing LEDs (light emitting diodes) in accordance with the music’s amplitude. The system was named the “Singing Illuminant.” The design of the Singing Illuminant is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The Singing Illuminant.

The Singing Illuminant was composed of a PC, an amplifier, and LEDs. LEDs were used because they can display a variety of colors and have the brightness of the display varies with the voltage supplied. The music reproduced by the PC was input to the amplifier, whose outputs were divided into three LEDs, one per circuit, according to the frequency range of the inputted music signal. It is possible to express various colors appropriate to the music by changing the colors of the LEDs.

circuit	range	[Hz]	LED
1	high range	500-8000	red
2	medium range	200-2400	green
3	low range	20-300	blue

Table 1. Frequency range

Table 1 lists the frequency range of the Singing Illuminant. If the frequency of the music was increased, the system also increased the brightness of the lights. The outputted LED light was diffused by round lampshades made of Japanese paper. Accordingly, the light was presented in the soft mode on the plane emission.

Figure 4. Exterior of the Singing Illuminant.

Examples of the exterior of the Singing Illuminant are shown in Figure 4. The music used featured various instruments, each with its own frequency range. Therefore, the system adjusted its circuits in accordance with the frequency range of the music, blending the color of the lights in the lampshade accordingly.

In order to confirm the feasibility of the Singing Illuminant, we tested it at stage productions of Georges Bizet’s opera “Carmen” (sponsored by Kanazawa Art Promotion and Development at

Kanazawa Theatre) and Kyoka Izumi’s play “The Water Magician” (sponsored by Kanazawa Junior Chamber Incorporated at the Kanazawa Yugure Festival). The Singing Illuminant was generally accepted by the audience as a lighting effect.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The purpose of our chosen experiment was to analyze the differences between the effects of music and lighting. We used a story from an actual opera, Vincenzo Bellini’s “I Puritani” (1834) in the experiment. “I Puritani” is composed of three acts. Acts I and II were used as the first half of the story, and Act III was used as the latter half. The first half of “I Puritani” is filled with sadness, whereas the second half features events. The intermission music between Acts II and III was used for musical stimulation. Lighting stimulation was visually expressed by the Singing Illuminant. The frequency range of the music was 75.4-1755 [Hz], which was within the range of the Singing Illuminant. The subjects that viewed the lighting stimulation were termed “the lighting group,” whereas the subjects that heard the musical stimulation were termed “the music group.”

Step 1 7 min	Read the first half of the story	
Step 2 2 min	Lighting group	Music group
	See the lighting	Listen to the music
Step 3 13 min	Describe what they expected would happen next in the story when seeing the lighting	Describe what they expected would happen next in the story when listening to the music
Step 4	Read the latter half of the story	

Figure 5. Procedure for the experiment.

The procedure for the experiment is shown in Figure 5. The subjects read the first half of the story, after which, subjects in the lighting group saw the lighting, while subjects in the music group listened to the music. Subjects then described what they expected would happen in the second part of the story. Either music or lighting was presented to each subject in this step, and subjects were instructed to describe as many of their anticipations as they could. The statements given by the subjects in this step were expected to involve their active impressions. Finally, subjects read the latter half of the story. Subjects

were questioned about their demographic information (age, etc.) and the stimulation.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

The data obtained in the experiment were analyzed as follows.

First, the statements given during the anticipation description phase were parsed through a morphological analysis system and classified under three categories: GIVEN, ASSOCIATED, and IMAGINED. The words classified under “GIVEN” were included in the first half of the story. The words classified under “ASSOCIATED” were determined to be associated with the words classified under the “GIVEN” category using the associative concept dictionary (Okamoto and Ishizaki, 2001), which is based on people’s associations. All other words were classified under the “IMAGINED” category. These categories are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Classification of words.

Furthermore, the degree of detail of the words was measured by using the EDR (EDR Concept Dictionary, 2005), a thesaurus with a layered structure. The upper word is the more abstract word, whereas the lower word is more concrete. Using the top word “concept,” we assumed that the number of layers from “concept” to a given word involves the degree of detail of that word.

Additionally, all described sentences were read by the reviewers and the degrees of “Happiness” and “Sadness” of each sentence were evaluated using five-point scales (with five being “most happy” or “most sad”). The reviewers read the first half of the story and then evaluated the sentences according to the following rules:

- The sum of the scores for “Happiness” and “Sadness” could be more or less than five.

- If the reviewer found a word that carried a happy or other positive feeling in the sentence, then the reviewer added a point to “Happiness.”
- If the reviewer found a word that carried a sad or other negative feeling in the sentence, then the reviewer added a point to “Sadness.”

RESULTS

Twelve subjects (aged 22-52) participated in the experiment. It was confirmed that they did not know the story used in the experiment and had not seen “I Puritani.” Six subjects were assigned to the lighting group and six to the music group.

	Number of sentences	
	Total	Mean
Lighting group	35	5.83
Music group	24	4.00

Table 2. Result of described sentences

Table 2 lists the number of sentences given by the subjects. A marginal difference was found between the mean of the number of described sentences ($t(10) = 2.20, p = .052$). Subjects in the lighting group described more anticipations than those in the music group.

Figure 7. Results of the classification of words.

	GIVEN	ASSOCIATED	IMAGINED
Lighting group	-5.824**	4.628**	1.778+
Music group	5.824**	-4.628**	-1.778+

** p < 0.01, + p < 0.10

Table 3. Residual analysis

The described words were classified according to the categories mentioned above, as shown in Figure 7. The numbers in the figure represent the number of

words that was classified under each category. In the chi-square test for assessing the distribution ratio of the classified words, a significant difference was found between the lighting and music groups ($\chi^2(2) = 38.17, p < .01$). Table 3 presents the results of the residual analysis. These results indicate that the distribution ratio of ASSOCIATED words of the lighting group was higher than that of the music group, whereas the distribution ratio of the GIVEN words was lower.

	Type of words			Degree of detail of the words	
	Total	Excepted	Measured	Mean	S.D.
Lighting group	242	75	167	6.92*	1.67
Music group	178	68	110	7.37*	1.77

S.D. = Standard Deviation, * $p < 0.05$

Table 4. Measures of the degree of detail of the words

Figure 8. The degree of detail of the words (error bars indicate the standard error of mean), * $p < 0.05$.

The results of measuring the degree of detail of the words are presented in Table 4. In order to clarify the differences between the lighting group and the music group, the words that were described by both groups were excluded. Words that were not in the EDR, such as characters' names, were also excluded. Figure 8 shows the means of the degree of detail of the words. There is a significant difference between the lighting group and the music group ($t(275) = 2.17, p = .031$). The words described by the music group were found to be more detailed than those described by the lighting group.

	Happiness		Sadness	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Lighting group	2.83**	1.32**	3.15**	1.30
Music group	1.90**	1.10	3.86**	1.18

** $p < 0.01, * p < 0.05$

Table 5. Evaluation of "Happiness" and "Sadness"

Figure 9. Comparing the variance (error bars indicate the standard deviation).

The result of the "Sadness" and "Happiness" degree evaluation is presented in Table 5. The reviewers were five people who did not participate in the experiment. The mean values for "Happiness" and "Sadness" were significantly different between both the lighting group and the music group: "Happiness" ($t(282) = 6.62, p < .001$) and "Sadness" ($t(293) = -4.79, p < .001$). The lighting group wrote more "Happy" sentences than the music group. Figure 9 compares the evaluations of variance. Regarding "Happiness," there is a significant different variance between the lighting group and the music group ($F(174, 119) = 1.45, p = .031$). On the other hand, there was no significant difference for "Sadness" between the groups ($F(174, 119) = 1.20, n.s.$).

DISCUSSION

Here, we discuss the results of the experiment based on the model of active impressions shown in Figure 1 by focusing on the effects of the media. First, we focused on the effects of the media on the process of active impressions. The subjects in the lighting group described more sentences than the subjects in the music group (Table 2). Moreover, as presented in Table 3, the subjects in the lighting group described more ASSOCIATED words than the subjects in the music group. Accordingly, we assume that the subjects in the lighting group made more associations than those in the music group. Next, we focused on the degree of detail of the words presented in Table 4. We found that the degree given by the music group was higher than that given by the lighting group. This result indicates

that the subjects in the music group wrote more concrete anticipations than the subjects in the lighting group.

Furthermore, from the results listed in Table 5, we infer that the subjects in the lighting group imagined more happy endings, whereas the subjects in the music group imagined more sad endings. In addition, the variance of the evaluated value of the lighting group was higher than that of the music group for "Happiness." This implies that the subjects in the lighting group described more anticipations than the subjects in the music group.

Based on these results, we infer that lighting may lead to various associations; hence, subjects who were presented with the lighting display wrote many anticipations. On the other hand, music may induce a passive effect on impressions.

From the results of the experiment, we can infer that lighting causes more active impressions than music. This result indicates that active impressions may be affected by the medium wherein the impressions are generated and received.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this study, we discussed active impressions and effects of various media on them. By focusing on the visual and auditory senses, we investigated the difference between light and music. To analyze this difference, we performed an experiment based on the structure of an opera. The results of the experiment indicate that the medium affects the active impressions wherein impressions are generated and received.

Subjects remarked, "By seeing the brightness and the color of the lighting, I imagined what would happen next," and "I associated the increasing tension of the story with the flow of the music." The impressions given by the lighting may be more ambiguous, which may relate to the difference in active impressions.

Accordingly, it is hoped that active impressions are involved in the users' feelings with the products and that the study of active impressions will be of some use to the design of products that elicit a novel response from users.

However, we cannot determine precisely why the medium affects active impressions based on the data

from our experiment. In particular, this study was conducted on only one type of each medium. Further study should be conducted.

Now, in another study, we are developing a method of designing creative and emotional motion (movement of an object) (Yamada et al., 2010). This method is based on the hypothesis that the motion beyond ordinary human imagination can produce emotional impressions that cause deep feelings internally. That is, the motion that extends beyond ordinary human imagination may elicit these impressions from within us. The designed motion is expected to appeal to the visual and auditory senses. In that study, we confirmed that the designed motions are effective in producing more creative and more emotional impressions. However, we cannot design creative and emotional motion in a systematic way without knowing how the visual and auditory senses affect these impressions.

We believe that the findings obtained in this study can contribute to emotional design not only for the abovementioned motion design but also for product design in general.

REFERENCES

- EDR Concept Dictionary*. (2005) CPD-V030, NICT, Japan.
- LeDoux, J.E. (1996) *The emotional brain: the mysterious underpinnings of emotional life*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Marr, D. (1982) *Vision: a computational investigation into the human representation and processing of visual information*. San Francisco: W. H. Freeman.
- Neisser, U. (1976) *Cognition and reality: principles and implications of cognitive psychology*. San Francisco: W. H. Freeman.
- Okamoto, J., Ishizaki S. (2001) Associative concept dictionary construction and its comparison with electronic concept dictionaries. *PACLING2001*, 214-220.
- Sadie, S., Tyrrell, J. (Eds.) (2001) *The New Grove Dictionary of Music and Musicians*, 2nd edition. New York: Grove's Dictionaries.
- Taura, T., Yamamoto, E., Fasiha, M.Y.N., Nagai, Y. (2010) Virtual impression networks for capturing deep impressions. *Design Computing and Cognition 10*, Springer-Verlag, 559-578.
- Vickery, G., Wunch-Vincent, S. (2007) Web and user-created content: Web 2.0, wikies and social networking. *OECD Work on Digital Content*.
- Yamada, K., Nagai, Y., Taura, T. (2011) Study of the Medium's Effect on Active Impressions. *Memoirs of the Graduate Schools of Engineering and System Informatics Kobe University No.3*.
- Yamada, K., Taura, T., Nagai, Y. (2010) Design of Emotional and Creative Motion by Focusing on Rhythmic Features. *Design Creativity 2010*, Springer-Verlag, 139-146.